

Men's Perspective: Investigating the Perceived Impact of Paternity on Software Engineering

Thank you for participating in our study on impact of paternity on Software Engineering: a Men's Perspective.

The purpose of this study is to investigate the challenges fathers face in global software development teams.

The survey will take about 12 minutes.

STATEMENT OF INFORMED CONSENT

By answering this survey, you allow the researchers to obtain, use and disclose the anonymous information provided as described below.

CONDITIONS AND STIPULATIONS

1. I understand that all information is confidential. I will not be personally identified. I agree to complete the survey for research purposes and that the data derived from this anonymous survey may be published in journals, conferences and blog posts.
2. I understand that my participation in this research survey is totally voluntary, and that declining to participate will involve no penalty or loss of benefits. If I choose, I may withdraw my participation at any time. I also understand that if I choose to participate, that I may decline to answer any question that I am not comfortable answering.
3. I understand that I can contact the researchers if I have any questions about the research survey. I am aware that my consent will not directly benefit me. I am also aware that the author will maintain the data collected in perpetuity and may utilize data for future academic work.
4. By consenting to participate, I freely provide consent and acknowledge my rights as a voluntary research participant as outlined above and provide consent to the researchers to use my information in conducting research on the areas noted above.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

1. Consent to participate in the research *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Agree

Disagree *Pular para a seção 3 (You cannot participate)*

Father Requirement

2. 1. Are you a father (biological father, stepfather or adoptive father)? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

No *Pular para a seção 3 (You cannot participate)*

Yes *Pular para a pergunta 3*

You cannot participate

Sorry, but our survey requires you to agree with our terms and be a father.

General Profile

3. 2. In what country do you live? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Afghanistan
- Albania
- Algeria
- Andorra
- Angola
- Antigua & Deps
- Argentina
- Armenia
- Australia
- Austria
- Azerbaijan
- Bahamas
- Bahrain
- Bangladesh
- Barbados
- Belarus
- Belgium
- Belize
- Benin
- Bhutan
- Bolivia
- Bosnia Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Brazil
- Brunei
- Bulgaria
- Burkina
- Burundi
- Cambodia
- Cameroon
- Canada
- Cape Verde

- Central African Rep
- Chad
- Chile
- China
- Colombia
- Comoros
- Congo
- Congo {Democratic Rep}
- Costa Rica
- Croatia
- Cuba
- Cyprus
- Czech Republic
- Denmark
- Djibouti
- Dominica
- Dominican Republic
- East Timor
- Ecuador
- Egypt
- El Salvador
- Equatorial Guinea
- Eritrea
- Estonia
- Ethiopia
- Fiji
- Finland
- France
- Gabon
- Gambia
- Georgia
- Germany
- Ghana
- Greece
- Grenada

Guatemala

Guinea

Guinea-Bissau

Guyana

Haiti

Honduras

Hungary

Iceland

India

Indonesia

Iran

Iraq

Ireland {Republic}

Israel

Italy

Ivory Coast

Jamaica

Japan

Jordan

Kazakhstan

Kenya

Kiribati

Korea North

Korea South

Kosovo

Kuwait

Kyrgyzstan

Laos

Latvia

Lebanon

Lesotho

Liberia

Libya

Liechtenstein

Lithuania

- Luxembourg
- Macedonia
- Madagascar
- Malawi
- Malaysia
- Maldives
- Mali
- Malta
- Marshall Islands
- Mauritania
- Mauritius
- Mexico
- Micronesia
- Moldova
- Monaco
- Mongolia
- Montenegro
- Morocco
- Mozambique
- Myanmar, {Burma}
- Namibia
- Nauru
- Nepal
- Netherlands
- New Zealand
- Nicaragua
- Niger
- Nigeria
- Norway
- Oman
- Pakistan
- Palau
- Panama
- Papua New Guinea
- Paraguay

Peru

Philippines

Poland

Portugal

Qatar

Romania

Russian Federation

Rwanda

St Kitts & Nevis

St Lucia

Saint Vincent & the Grenadines

Samoa

San Marino

Sao Tome & Principe

Saudi Arabia

Senegal

Serbia

Seychelles

Sierra Leone

Singapore

Slovakia

Slovenia

Solomon Islands

Somalia

South Africa

South Sudan

Spain

Sri Lanka

Sudan

Suriname

Swaziland

Sweden

Switzerland

Syria

Taiwan

- Tajikistan
- Tanzania
- Thailand
- Togo
- Tonga
- Trinidad & Tobago
- Tunisia
- Turkey
- Turkmenistan
- Tuvalu
- Uganda
- Ukraine
- United Arab Emirates
- United Kingdom
- United States
- Uruguay
- Uzbekistan
- Vanuatu
- Vatican City
- Venezuela
- Vietnam
- Yemen
- Zambia
- Zimbabwe

4. In what state do you live? *

5. How old are you? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- under 21 years old
- 21 to 25 years
- 26 to 30 years
- 31 to 36 years
- 37 to 42 years
- 43 to 47 years
- 48 to 54 anos
- 55 to 60 years
- more than 61 years
- Prefer not to answer

6. What is your marital status? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Single
- Married
- Long-term relationship
- Widowed
- Separated
- Divorced
- Prefer not to answer

7. What is the highest level of education you have completed? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- PhD
- Master
- Especialization
- Graduated
- Undergraduate Student

Children

8. How many children do you have (they can be biological, adopted or stepchild)? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- More than 5

9. How old is your youngest child? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- Between 4 and 6 years
- Between 7 and 9 years
- Between 10 and 12 years
- More than 12 years

10. Do your child (or children) live with you? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

Professional Life

11. What is your family income? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Up to 3 minimum wages
- Up to 5 minimum wages
- Up to 7 minimum wages
- Up to 9 minimum wages
- More than 10 minimum wages

12. Are you currently employed? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- No
- Yes, and I work remotely/from home
- Yes, and I work face to face/in-person
- Yes, and I work in hybrid mode (remotely and face to face)

13. What is the nature of your organization? *

You can tick more than one if you work for more than one company.

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Federal Public Administration
- State Public Administration
- Private software development companies
- State-owned company (Serpro, state banks, and so on.)
- Research/collaboration projects
- Open source software projects

14. Do you work in the software industry or academia? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Industry *Pular para a pergunta 15*
- Academia *Pular para a pergunta 18*
- Industry and Academia *Pular para a pergunta 20*

15. How many years of experience do you have in software industry ? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- Between 4 and 6 years
- Between 7 and 9 years
- Between 10 and 12 years
- Between 13 and 15 years
- More than 15 years

16. How many employees does the organization have? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Up to 20 employees
- From 21 to 49 employees
- From 50 to 99 employees
- From 100 to 199 employees
- From 200 to 399 employees
- From 400 to 599 employees
- More than 600 employees

17. How many members are there on your team? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 5
- From 6 to 10
- From 11 to 15
- From 16 to 20
- More than 21

Work in Academia

18. How many years of experience do you have as a researcher or professor? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- Between 4 and 6 years
- Between 7 and 9 years
- Between 10 and 12 years
- Between 13 and 15 years
- More than 15 years

19. How many members are there on your department/Institution? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Up to 20 members
- From 21 to 49 members
- From 50 to 99 members
- From 100 to 199 members
- From 200 to 399 members
- From 400 to 599 members
- More than 600 members

Pular para a pergunta 25

Work in Industry & Academia

20. How many years of experience do you have in **software industry** ? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- Between 4 and 6 years
- Between 7 and 9 years
- Between 10 and 12 years
- Between 13 and 15 years
- More than 15 years

21. Regarding your **industry** experience. How many employees does the organization have? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Up to 20 employees
- From 21 to 49 employees
- From 50 to 99 employees
- From 100 to 199 employees
- From 200 to 399 employees
- From 400 to 599 employees
- More than 600 employees

22. Regarding your **industry** experience. How many members are there on your team? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 5
- From 6 to 10
- From 11 to 15
- From 16 to 20
- More than 21

23. Regarding your **academic** experience. How many years of experience do you have as a researcher or professor? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 3 years
- Between 4 and 6 years
- Between 7 and 9 years
- Between 10 and 12 years
- Between 13 and 15 years
- More than 15 years

24. Regarding your **academic** experience. How many members are there on your department/Institution? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Up to 20 members
- From 21 to 49 members
- From 50 to 99 members
- From 100 to 199 members
- From 200 to 399 members
- From 400 to 599 members
- More than 600 members

Pular para a pergunta 25

Organization

25. What is the main role you perform in the organization? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Requirements Analyst
- Data Modeling
- Software Engineer
- Programmer/Developer
- Software Tester
- Designer
- Project Manager
- Human-Computer Interaction specialist
- Researcher
- Professor
- Professor and Researcher
- Outro: _____

26. How many women are there on your team or department? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Less than 3
- From 4 to 6
- From 7 to 10
- From 11 to 15
- From 16 to 20
- More than 21

27. How many women have leadership positions in your team or department? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- None
- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5
- More than 5

Back to Work

28. How long was your paternity leave? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- I did not take paternity leave
- from 1 to 5 days
- from 6 to 10 days
- from 11 to 20 days
- from 21 to 30 days
- from 31 to 40 days
- from 41 to 50 days
- from 51 to 60 days
- from 61 to 120 days
- more than 120 days

29. Would you like your paternity leave to be longer? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- No, it was enough.
- Yes, I'd like more days.

30. Did you return to the same position and company after becoming father? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes, same role and company
- No, another role and same company
- No, same role and another company
- No, another role and another company

31. If you have changed your position and/or company, could you talk a little about your motivation for the change?

You can answer in Portuguese or English.

32. How many employments did you have before becoming father? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- None
- 1
- 2
- 3
- More than 3

33. Did you maintain the same number of employment relationships after becoming father? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

34. Did you work during your paternity leave? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No
- Partially

35. If you worked during your paternity leave, what were the reasons that led you to work during this period?

You can answer in Portuguese or English.

Pular para a pergunta 37

I was not employed when becoming father

36. After you returned to work, did you get a part-time job or a full time-job? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Part-time job
- Full-time job
- Outro: _____

Paternity

37. Who performs more child care activities when both are present or when both are able to perform? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- I tend to do more childcare activities than my partner.
- The mother does more.
- We do share child caregiving equally.
- Outro: _____

38. Would you like to participate more in parenting activities? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Yes
- No

39. If you do not contribute equally to parenting activities, what are the reasons? *

You can answer in Portuguese or English.

40. After becoming father, have you faced any of the following situations? *

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- Lack of confidence
- Overload (related to child activities and attention)
- High physical and mental exhaustion (related to child activities and attention)
- Sleep deprivation (related to child activities and attention)
- Guilty (related to child activities and attention)
- Outro: _____

41. Have you ever faced any type of prejudice at work for being a father? *

You can answer in Portuguese or English.

Perceptions

42. In your opinion, do you think that **women** suffer any kind of distrust at work for being a mother?

Examples of distrust: do not getting greater responsibilities because she is now a mother, do not be capable of completing a task...

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Definitely
- Probably
- Possibly
- Probably Not
- Definitely Not

43. In your opinion, do you think that **women** suffer any kind of moral harassment (for example, mean joke and prejudice) for being a mother?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Definitely
- Probably
- Possibly
- Probably Not
- Definitely Not

Final Questions: Difficulties and Challenges

44. What challenges and difficulties do you face at work as a father? *

You can answer in Portuguese or English.

45. In your opinion, what challenges and difficulties mothers face at work? *

You can answer in Portuguese or English.

46. At work, do you believe that mothers face more difficulties for being a mother than fathers face for being a father? Discuss about it. *

You can answer in Portuguese or English.

47. What are your suggestions to mitigate the difficulties that **parents** (father and mother) face at work? *

You can answer in Portuguese or English.

48. Are you willing to implement friendly actions for moms and dads at work? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Definitely

Probably

Possibly

Probably Not

Definitely Not

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